

Assessment of Seismic Hazard for the District of Jalandhar (India) in view of Smart City Mission

Research Paper

Gagan Deep¹ and Nitish Puri²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, LKCE, Jalandhar (Punjab), India

²Consultant, AECOM India Private Limited, Chennai (Tamil Nadu), India

*Corresponding Author's Email: nitish.puri@aecom.com

*ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4936-3905>

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ABSTRACT

Probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA) has been carried out for the district of Jalandhar. The earthquake data has been collected from different seismological agencies, e.g. NDMA, IMD, ISC-UK and USGS, and a comprehensive earthquake catalogue has been developed. Several ground motion prediction equations have been reviewed to select a GMPE appropriate for carrying out PSHA. Earthquake hazard parameters have been estimated for PGA and spectral acceleration. The seismic hazard maps of district have been developed for different return periods at 10%, 2% and 1% probability of exceedance. The results show that the district can experience strong shaking from earthquakes originating in north-west Himalayas. Nonlinear site response analysis has also been carried out for limited number of sites in order to investigate the effect of local site conditions on earthquake ground motions. It has been observed that the soils of district of Jalandhar are capable of amplifying earthquake ground motions. Therefore, structures must be designed using the hazard parameters determined considering the local tectonic setup of the region as well as the local soil conditions. The developed hazard maps would help engineers and architects involved in planning and design of earthquake resistant structures and retrofitting works.

Keywords: PSHA, Maximum magnitude potential, Peak ground acceleration, Spectral acceleration, Jalandhar

INTRODUCTION

Smart cities keep track of the condition of critical infrastructure facilities, which include water supply network, rain water and waste water drainage systems, fuel supply and storage systems, electricity supply units, communication systems, transportation systems and building services, to better optimize resources, plan maintenance activities, arrange immediate rescue in case of both natural and man-made hazards, and monitor security aspects while maximizing services to citizens. In India, a number of smart cities have been planned in various states, e.g. Karnal and Faridabad in the State of Haryana, Ludhiana, Jalandhar and Amritsar in the State of Punjab, New Delhi in the Union Territory

of Delhi and Chandigarh city in the Union Territory Chandigarh. The Smart City Mission is a centrally sponsored scheme financed by the Government of India with funds up to ₹480 billion in a duration of five years. Retrofitting is the primary strategic component of area-based development in the Smart City Mission. Structures that need to be retrofitted in a city would be identified to build intensive infrastructure facilities with smart applications packed in a Smart City. Planning of an efficient retrofitting in a city requires good knowledge of various expected hazards, e.g. flood hazard, wind hazard and earthquake hazard.

The present study focuses on the assessment of earthquake hazard for the district of

 Corresponding Author's Affiliation:
AECOM India Private Limited
ASV Ramana Towers, 3rd Floor,
T Nagar, CIT Nagar East, T. Nagar, Chennai, Tamil Nadu 600017

Jalandhar in State of Punjab (India) in view of planning for the proposed smart city 'Jalandhar'.

The earthquake zoning map of the India reported in IS 1893-Part1(2016), offers a broad zoning of the country for seismic hazard, and it gets updated only when new earthquakes occur. Hence, it is necessary to obtain reliable estimates of seismic hazard parameters calculated by carrying out state-of-the-art analysis on possible earthquake scenarios. The results of such analyses are formulated generally in terms of peak ground acceleration (PGA) and spectral acceleration (Sa) at various return periods. PGA is used to quantify earthquake ground motions, horizontal forces and shear stresses and strains in the earthquake resistant design procedures. Whereas, Sa is a crude representation of the response of a structure represented by the maximum acceleration experienced by single-degree-of-freedom system undergoing damped vibrations.

The local soil conditions in top 20 to 30 m of soil profile play an important role in defining the characteristics of earthquake ground motions reaching at the surface of the earth. Site response analysis is often carried out to assess the effect of local soil conditions on earthquake wave propagation. The results of ground response analysis are expressed in terms of amplification factors for PGA and Sa. The values of PGA and Sa for rock sites, obtained from either deterministic or probabilistic seismic hazard assessments can be suitably modified using the amplification factors obtained from site response analysis.

In the present study, probabilistic seismic hazard analysis and nonlinear site response analysis has been performed for the district of Jalandhar, and seismic hazard maps based on PGA and Sa have been prepared at various return periods. The developed hazard maps along with the suggested amplification factors would help engineers and architects involved in planning and design of earthquake resistant structures and retrofitting works in the District.

STUDY AREA AND TECTONIC MAP

The entire Jalandhar Division was awarded to India when Punjab was partitioned. Jalandhar District, with population of about 2.19 million is the 4th most populated district in the state of Punjab. The district of Jalandhar is the 9th biggest district in terms of area in the state of Punjab with an approximate geographical area of about 2624 km². The population density in the district is approximately 836 people per km².

The region has experienced some mild seismic activity in the past in the range of M 4.0-5.0. On 14th March 2010, the region experienced a mild earthquake of magnitude of 4.5, that occurred in northern Punjab along the Punjab-Himachal Pradesh border. It was felt over a wide area due to its shallow depth near Hiranagar (Punjab). In August 2013, another mild intensity earthquake of magnitude 4.7 on the Richter's scale was felt at many places in Punjab. The epicenter of the quake was in the Hoshiarpur-Himachal Pradesh border region as per India Metrological Department (IMD). However, some disastrous earthquakes have also occurred near the region in the last 200 years, which are 1934 Bihar-Nepal earthquake (Mw 8.4), 1950 Assam earthquake (Mw 8.7), 1905 Kangra earthquake (Mw 7.8), 1991 Uttarkashi (Mw 6.8), 1993 Killari earthquake (Mw 6.2), 1999 Chamoli earthquake (Mw 6.8), 2005 Kashmir earthquake (Mw 7.6) and 2015 Gorkha earthquake (Mw 7.8). The havoc produced by these earthquakes has been a wakeup call for the government to take suitable mitigation measures.

An area of 300 km radius around Jalandhar district has been selected as the seismic study region (28-34 Degree N to 72-78 Degree E). A tectonic map developed for the seismic study region by Puri and Jain (2018) has been adopted for the study (Fig. 1). The tectonic map was developed using SEISAT (Dasgupta et al., 2000). The potential earthquake hazard in the study area is governed by several tectonic features, which include Himalayan Frontal Thrust on the north and north-eastern side, local lineaments on the south and Sargodha-Lahore-Delhi ridge on the north-western side.

ESTIMATION OF GUTENBERG-RICHTER PARAMETERS

The development of a comprehensive catalogue of seismic events is a first step for any seismic hazard assessment program. A reliable estimate of earthquake hazard in a region strongly depends on the accuracy and adequacy of the information on earthquake events. Information on damaging earthquakes that have occurred during pre-instrumental period has been collected from the catalogue developed by National Disaster

Management Authority of India (NDMA). The earthquake data for the instrumental period have been collected from various international and national earthquake monitoring agencies, e.g. United States Geological Survey (USGS), India Meteorological Department (IMD) and National Disaster Management Agency (NDMA), India (NDMA, 2011), and International Seismological Centre, UK (ISC-UK). An earthquake catalogue has been developed, for 1800 AD to 2017 AD, by combining the pre-instrumental and instrumental data.

Fig. 1. Tectonic setup of the seismic study region (after Puri and Jain, 2018)

Table 1. Completeness analysis of catalogue

Magnitude class (M _w)	Completeness			
	CUVI method		Stepp method	
	Period	Interval (Years)	Period	Interval (Years)
4.0-4.9	1962-2015	53	1963-2015	52
5.0-5.9	1926-2015	89	1925-2015	90
6.0-6.9	1901-1975	74	1900-1970	70
7.0-7.9	1905-1999	94	1904-1999	95

The events with earthquake magnitudes other than M_w have been converted using the available empirical relationships between various earthquake magnitude scales and moment magnitude (M_w). Pre-instrumental data is usually available on MMI scale and has been changed to moment magnitude by Gutenberg-Richter equation, which is as follows:

$$M_w = 2/3 \times MMI + 1 \quad (1)$$

The correlations developed by Scordilis (2008) between $m_b - M_w$ and $M_s - M_w$ have been used.

The following correlation derived by Kolathayar et al. (2012) has been considered for the conversion of local magnitude to moment magnitude.

$$M_w = 0.815 \times M_L + 0.767, \text{ for } 3.3 \leq M_L \leq 7.0 \quad (2)$$

The following correlation developed by Yenier et al. (2008) between $M_d - M_w$ has been used.

$$M_w = 0.764 \times M_d + 1.379, \text{ for } 3.7 \leq M_d \leq 6.0 \quad (3)$$

An epicentral map has been developed using the prepared catalogue (Fig. 2). The catalogue has been checked for completeness using CUVI (Tinti and Mulargia, 1985) and Stepp method (Stepp, 1972) and found to be complete for a sufficient period of time. The completion periods have been reported in the Table 1. The compiled catalogue contains 1256 earthquake events of moment magnitude (M_w) ≥ 4 that have occurred up to December 2017 in the study region.

For identifying potential seismogenic sources, the epicenters from the compiled catalogue (Fig. 2) have been plotted over tectonic map (Fig. 1). A total of 10 tectonic features associated with earthquakes of $M_w \geq 4.0$ have been identified as active seismogenic sources, out of these, 8 sources are potential seismogenic sources as given in table below.

The earthquakes of $M_w \geq 5$ have been considered for M_{max} estimation. The M_{max} values for the major seismogenic sources in the study area have been estimated by adding an increment 0.5 to the respective values of M_{obs} (Gupta, 2002). The

calculated M_{max} values for study region are between moment magnitude of 5.5 to 8.5 (Table 3).

The Gutenberg-Richter seismicity parameters a and b are the prime input parameters in PSHA and hence need to be calculated with precision. For this, the study region was divided into three sub-regions considering each sub-region as an area source of earthquakes. The seismicity parameters were computed for each area source through linear least squares regression method following an exponential distribution of magnitude taking into account the complete part of the catalogue for all the magnitude classes. The exponential distribution is given in equation (4) below:

$$\lambda_m = 10^{a-bM_w} = \exp(\alpha - \beta M_w) \quad (4)$$

where, λ_m = mean yearly rate of exceedance, a = coefficient such that a^{th} power of 10 gives the mean annual number of earthquakes of magnitude ≥ 0 , $\alpha = 2.303a$, b = coefficient that describes the possibility of large and small earthquakes and $\beta = 2.303b$.

The reciprocal of λ_m for a given magnitude is called return period (T_R) of an earthquake exceeding that magnitude and is very important for earthquake resistant design. The seismicity of all area sources considered in the study has been calculated and reported in Table 4. The value of return period calculated for different area sources demonstrates the capability of tectonic sources in Himalayan Thrust System to generate frequent large earthquakes.

Assesement of Seismic Hazard

The global ground motion prediction equation developed by Abrahamson et al. (2013) has been used for the estimation of earthquake hazard. PSHA has been done considering three sub-regions, viz. Himalayan Thrust System, Sargodha-Lahore-Delhi Ridge and Aravalli-Delhi Fold Belt as area sources of earthquakes and based on the developed catalogue, average focal depths have been taken as 15 km, 17 km and 10 km for the selected three sub-regions, respectively.

Fig. 2. Epicenter Map of Study Area

Table 2. Maximum Observed Magnitudes for Various Sources

S. No.	Seismogenic Source	M_{obs}
1.	Jwala Mukhi Thrust (JMT)	5.5
2.	Kaurik Fault System (KFS)	6.8
3.	Lineament System of SLDR (LSLDR)	6
4.	Main Boundary Thrust (MBT)	8
5.	Main Frontal Thrust (MFT)	5
6.	Main Crustral Thrust (MCT)	7.3
7.	Sundar Nagar Fault (SNF)	7
8.	Sargodha Lahore Delhi Ridge (SLDR)	6.5

Table 3. M_{max} values for Various Sources

Seismogenic Source	Total Length of Fault (in km)	M_{max}
Sargodha Lahore Delhi Ridge (SLDR)	Area Source	7
Main Boundary Thrust (MBT)	825	8.5
Main Frontal Thrust (MFT)	32	5.5
Jwala Mukhi Thrust (JMT)	290	6.0
Main Crustral Thrust (MCT)	769	7.8
Sundar Nagar Fault (SNF)	101	7.5
Kaurik Fault System (KFS)	137	7.3
Lineament System of SLDR (LSLDR)	97	6.5

Table 4. Seismicity parameters for different area sources

Area source	b	a	Magnitude (M_w) class
Himalayan Thrust System	0.75	3.8	4.0-8.0
Aravalli-Delhi Fold Belt	0.69	2.61	4.0-7.0
Sargodha-Lahore-Delhi Ridge	0.85	3.27	4.0-6.5

The hazard has been calculated for 10%, 2% and 1% probability of exceedance in time frame as 50 years as per recommendations of Eurocode 8: BS-EN 1998-1 (2005). For ordinary structures, the seismic hazard map for 10% probability of exceedance in 50 years is recommended. However, for important facilities like Nuclear Power Plants and other megastructures, the maps for 2% and 1% probability are used. The PSHA software R-CRISIS v. 18.2 (Ordaz and Salgado-Gálvez, 2017) has been used for the purpose. R-CRISIS allows the calculation of results for exceedance probability plots, set of stochastic events etc. The parameters such as a, b, M_{min} , M_{max} , λ_m and attenuation models are the input parameters, and PGA and PSA are the outputs.

The hazard maps have been prepared for return periods of 475 years, 2475 years and 4975 years at 10%, 2% and 1% probabilities of exceedance in 50 years respectively (Fig. 3 to Fig. 4). The estimated peak ground acceleration ranges from 0.08g - 0.13g, 0.15g - 0.26g and 0.23g - 0.34g at 10%, 2% and 1% probabilities of exceedance respectively. It has been observed that the IS code underestimates the hazard at 2% and 1% probability of exceedance. The response spectra have been constructed for various return periods corresponding to maximum observed PGA and shown in Fig. 5 along with those specified in IS 1893 Part-1 for comparison. Hazard maps based on spectral acceleration (g) at 0.1 sec, 0.2 sec, 1.0 sec and 2.0 sec at 10%, 2% and 1% probabilities of exceedance have been also developed (Fig. 6). It has been observed that the IS code underestimates the spectral acceleration at higher structural periods for all return periods. Hence, high rise buildings in these areas constructed as per current Indian Standards could receive damage during earthquakes. However, a detailed study on the effect of local site conditions would provide a deeper insight into the problem at

hand.

1D Site Response Analysis

Site response analysis has been carried out for 5 sites (Fig. 7) drilled up to refusal in District of Jalandhar. For this, one dimensional nonlinear model has been adopted to estimate the response using DEEPSOIL software (Hashash et al., 2016). The methodology has been adopted from Puri and Jain (2018). Based on geotechnical data collected, sites are classified as class D sites by calculating average SPT N-value of the profile as per the recommendations of NEHRP (FEMA 368, 2000).

The stiffness and damping of soil layer play fundamental role in estimating wave amplification parameters in seismic microzonation studies. The analysis requires characterization of the stiffness of an element of soil considering low strain shear modulus (G_{max}), variation of modulus ratio (G/G_{max}) and Damping (D) with cyclic strain amplitude (γ), and other parameters. Due to unavailability of in-situ Shear wave velocity (V_s) or Shear Modulus (G_{max}) recordings, a correlation between G_{max} - N developed by Ohsaki and Iwasaki (1973) for sandy soils has been used and shear modulus degradation ($G/G_{max-\gamma}$) and damping ratio (D- γ) curves developed by Darendeli (2001) have been used. The Darendeli curves require the value of coefficient of earth pressure at rest (K_o) for each layer in order to fit $G/G_{max-\gamma}$ curves and D- γ curves for each layer. The K_o values have been calculated using the following equation:

$$K_o = 1 - \sin \phi \quad (5)$$

where ϕ = angle of internal friction. The ϕ values have been estimated from SPT N-values using the correlation developed by Puri et al. (2018). The typical input parameters for site 4 have been reported in Table 5.

Fig. 3. Seismic Hazard Map of Jalandhar at 10% Probability of Exceedance in 50 years

Fig. 4. Seismic Hazard Map of Jalandhar at (a) 2% Probability of Exceedance in 50 years and (b) 1% Probability of Exceedance in 50 years

Fig. 5. Comparison of PSHA based response spectra with response spectra specified in IS 1893-Part 1:2016

Fig. 6. Spectral acceleration maps for various return periods of (a) 475-year at 0.1 sec. (b) 475-year at 0.2 sec. (c) 475-year at 1.0 sec. (d) 475-year at 2.0 sec. (e) 2475-year at 0.1 sec. (f) 2475-year at 0.2 sec

Fig. 6. Continued Spectral accelerations (g) for various return periods of (g) 2475-year at 1.0 sec. (h) 2475-year at 2.0 sec. (i) 4975-year at 0.1 sec. (j) 4975-year at 0.2 sec. (k) 4975-year at 1.0 sec. (l) 4975-year at 2.0 sec

Suitable acceleration time histories can be selected based on magnitude of controlling earthquake, PGA value, source to site distance and site class. PGA values obtained from PSHA for rock sites corresponding to a return period of 475 year have been used for the selection of input motions at each site. Acceleration time history of the 1991 Uttarkashi earthquake M_w 6.8 (focal depth = 10 km) recorded at the Ghansiali station with $PGA = 0.118g$ is used for the analysis (Fig. 8).

Fig.7. Location of boreholes used for site response analysis

Table 5. Typical input parameters for Site no. 4

Depth	Soil Type	PI	Unit weight (kN/m ³)	SPT 'N'	N vs Depth	G _{max} (Mpa)	G _{max} vs Depth	K ₀
1.5	Sand	NP	15.37	7		39.70		0.52
3	Sand	NP	15.65	10		55.51		0.51
4.5	Sand	NP	15.84	12		65.89		0.50
6	Sand	NP	17.16	26		136.30		0.43
7.5	Sand	NP	17.72	32		165.68		0.41
9	Sand	NP	18.20	37		189.90		0.38
10.5	Sand	NP	21.90	61		303.83		0.29
12	Sand	NP	23.56	73		359.71		0.24
13.5	Sand	NP	25.77	89		433.37		0.19
15	Sand	NP	26.19	92		447.08		0.18
16.5	Sand	NP	27.15	99		478.99		0.16
18	Sand	NP	20.38	50		252.03		0.33
19.5	Sand	NP	20.38	50		252.03		0.33

*NP = Non-plastic; K₀ = Coefficient of earth pressure at rest

Fig.8. Input acceleration time history of 1991 Uttarkashi earthquake recorded at Ghansiali station

The results of the wave amplification analysis have been reported in Table 6. Fig. 9 shows a comparison of PGA (g) and shear strain (%) observed at different sites. Due to limited borehole data (eight boreholes), interpretation cannot be made for the amplification trend across the District. However, based on significant amplification observed at five sites, it can be concluded that the city may experience high ground accelerations. Moreover, high strains are observed for all the five sites and there is a possibility of substantial settlements during an earthquake. The amplification factors for the analyzed sites range from 1.65 to 2.11 with an average value of 1.9. The maximum PGA of 0.249g and minimum PGA of 0.195g are observed for Bulandpur and Wazir Singh Enclave sites, respectively. Based on the average amplification factor observed for PGA, the region can experience PGAs ranging from 0.152g to 0.247g. However, a

more detailed study specifically on site-response analysis is required for the region. The amplification factors for spectral acceleration (average of all sites) have been shown in Fig. 10. It has been observed that at all structural periods the spectral acceleration has been amplified. This shows that the estimated seismic scenario for the District of Jalandhar is worse than that proposed by the Indian Seismic Code. Hence, at higher structural periods, severe dynamic loading could be inflicted to structures designed using current structural design and construction bylaws of India. The average amplification factors and the hazard maps presented in this study can be used in design and retrofitting of structures in district.

CONCLUSION

The assessment seismic hazard has been carried out using probabilistic approach for estimating hazard parameters for rock sites for district of Jalandhar. The district is always under the threat from earthquakes due to its proximity to Himalayan frontal fault. It has been observed that the district is prone to high to severe earthquake ground motions ranging from 0.152g to 0.247g. Hence, a comprehensive estimation of earthquake hazard for the region is required. The results of this study would help and motivate engineers and investigators involved in seismic design and retrofitting of structures and planning for mitigation measures.

Table 6. Results of site response analysis

Site No.	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Surface PGA (g)	Amplification Factor
1	31.38363	75.54201	0.205	1.74
2	31.28898	75.59628	0.244	2.07
3	31.34913	75.55048	0.23	1.95
4	31.37636	75.58831	0.249	2.11
5	31.32522	75.63357	0.195	1.65

Fig.9. Comparison of PGA (g) and Shear Strain (%) observed at different sites

Fig.10. Observed amplification factors for spectral acceleration (Sa)

REFERENCES

1. Abrahamson, N. A., Silva, W. J. and Kamai, R. (2013). "Update of the AS08 Ground-Motion Prediction Equations Based on the NGA-West2 Data Set". PEER Report 2013/04 Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center Headquarters, University of California, Berkeley.

2. Darendeli, M. B. (2001). "Development of a new family of normalized modulus reduction and material damping curves". Ph.D. diss., University of Texas.
3. Dasgupta, S., Pande, P., Ganguly, D., Iqbal, Z., Sanyal, K., Venkatraman, N.V., Dasgupta, S., Sural, B., Harendranath, L., Mazumdar, K., Sanyal, S., Roy, A., Das, L.K., Misra, P.S. and Gupta, H. (2000). "Seismotectonic Atlas of India and its Environs". Geological Survey of India, Calcutta.
4. Eurocode 8: BS-EN 1998-1 (2005). "Design of structures for earthquake resistance – part 1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings". European committee for standardization, Brussels.
5. FEMA 368 (2000). "National earthquake hazard reduction program (NEHRP) recommended provisions for seismic regulations for new buildings and other structures, part 1: Provisions". Building Seismic Safety Council (BSSC), USA.
6. Gupta, I. D. (2002). "The State of the Art in Seismic Hazard Analysis". ISET Journal of Earthquake Technology, Vol. 39, Issue 4, pp. 311-346.
7. Hashash, Y.M.A., Park, D., Tsai, C.C., Philips, C. and Groholski, D.R. (2016). "DEEPSOIL - 1-D Wave Propagation Analysis Program, Version 6.1, Tutorial and User Manual". University of Illinois at Urbana-Campaign.
8. IS 1893 - Part1 (2002). "Indian Standard Criteria for Earthquake Resistant Design of Structures, Part 1: General Provisions and Building". Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi.
9. Kolathayar, S., Sitharam, T.G. and Vipin, K.S. (2012). "Spatial variation of seismicity parameters across India and adjoining areas". Natural Hazards, Vol. 60, pp. 1365-1379, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-011-9898-1>.
10. Ohsaki, Y. and Iwasaki, R. (1973). "Dynamic shear moduli and Poisson's ratio of soil deposits". Soils and Foundations, Vol.13, No.4, pp. 61-73.
11. Ordaz, M. and Salgado-Gálvez, M. A. (2017). "R-CRISIS Validation and Verification Document". Technical Report, Mexico City, Mexico.
12. Puri, N. and Jain, A. (2018). "Possible Seismic Hazards in Chandigarh City of North-western India due to its proximity to Himalayan Frontal Thrust". J. Ind. Geophys. Union, Vol. 22, No. 5, pp. 485-506.
13. Puri, N., Prasad H. D. and Jain, A. (2018). "Prediction of Geotechnical Parameters Using Machine Learning Techniques". Procedia Computer Science, Vol. 125, pp. 509–517, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.12.066>.
14. Scordilis, E. M. (2006). "Empirical global relations converting Ms and mb to moment magnitude". J. Seismology, Vol. 10, pp. 225-236, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10950-006-9012-4>.
15. Stepp, J. C. (1972). "Analysis of the completeness of the earthquake sample in the Puget Sound area and its effects on statistical estimates of earthquakes hazard". In: Proceedings of International Conference on Microzonation for Safer Construction Research and Application, Seattle, Washington.
16. Tinti, S. and Mulargia, F. (1985). "Completeness analysis of a seismic catalog". Annales Geophysicae, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 407-414.
17. Yenier, E., Erdoğan, Ö. and Akkar, S. (2008). "Empirical relationships for magnitude and source-to-site distance conversions using recently compiled Turkish strong-ground motion database". Proceedings of 14th World Conf. on Earthquake Engineering, Beijing, China.

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